

Original Article

Silencing the Mother Tongue: Language Flattening and Identity Loss in Exit West

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Abstract

In an era of intensified global circulation, contemporary fiction often grapples with the politics of language, identity, and translatability. This article explores how Mohsin Hamid's *Exit West* employs a deliberate strategy of language flattening, a stylistic choice that eschews code-switching, idiomatic texture, and vernacular richness to produce a smooth, globally legible prose. Grounded in postcolonial language politics and postmonolingual theory, this study offers a close, qualitative reading of the novel. Rather than viewing linguistic omission as neutral, the analysis interprets it as a politically meaningful act that complicates the critical tendency to equate multilingualism with resistance. The paper adopts a single-text case study approach and concludes by proposing language flattening as a useful lens for analyzing style in other transnational Anglophone texts and suggests avenues for future comparative and reader-response research.

Keywords: Language flattening; Postmonolingualism; Code-switching; Stylistics; Postcolonial criticism; Translation studies

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INTRODUCTION

Language is not just a charged site of power in postcolonial writing, but also a habitual feeling. Since the late twentieth century, many writers from formerly colonized contexts have bent English as a language to their will, splicing and code-switching, to insist that their stories carry the depths of other languages (Ashcroft, Griffiths, & Tiffin, 1989; Ngũgĩ wa Thiong'o, 1986; Spivak, 1988). Rushdie's famously "chutnified" prose (1991), Díaz's torrential Spanglish (2007), and Adichie's Igbo inflections (2003) have attuned us to celebrate such instances as resistance and providing proof that the empire's language can be re-written. In this critical sense, language functions more than a mere piece of text and becomes discourse functioning as a tool of belonging and affective continuity (Hall, 1990; Yildiz, 2012). Untranslated fragments, as Simon (1999) puts it act as subtle reminders of the original language and culture. This idea is particularly important in postcolonial translation studies, where retaining untranslated words can challenge the dominance of the target language and validate the cultural identity of the source.

However, this article positions itself differently with arguing the refrain of code-switching in Mohsin Hamid's *Exit West* (2017) to be intentional. In a world where multilingualism is celebrated and often functions as an authenticity marker the refusal points towards the absence being deliberate with a purpose of an uninterrupted linguistic feel that does aesthetic, political, and affective work. The significance of this choice becomes clear when viewed in a context of contrasting opinions. Rebecca Walkowitz (2015) describes the novel as texts written for global comprehension. Critics of the novel (Damrosch, 2003; Siskind, 2014; Rosa, 2019; Tay, 2010) note how market pressures invite stylistic neutrality and eliminate idiomatic friction providing ease to global readership. Postcolonial language politics, then, often appears split between two poles: exuberant hybridity and readable neutrality. The question is not simply which side a writer chooses but rather the implications of that choice and what it does to the representation of identity and displacement.

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Scholars have often focused on *Exit West*'s use of magical doors, interpreting them as metaphors for migration and the collapse of borders in a globalized world (Chakraborty, 2020), its subtle moments of kindness rooted in ethics of hospitality (Boehmer, 2020), and its temporal portrayal of politics (DeLoughrey, 2020). Meanwhile, Studies of postcolonial multilingualism analyze texts that flaunt hybridity but very few theorize the other way round, contemplating the nativization of language being absent and its implications. Yildiz's (2012) postmonolingual framework urges notice of how monolingual norms persist beneath the celebration of multilingualism, yet *Exit West* has not been central to that conversation. When critics observe this (Caton, 2021), it is often interpreted as a way to universalize the refugee and not as an enactment of loss.

Therefore, this study argues that Hamid (2017) practices language flattening as a device to negate markers of the protagonists' mother tongue from the narrated discourse so that a neutralized form of language mirrors their slow detachment from community. Two guiding questions shape the study i.e how does Hamid's linguistic choice represent cultural dislocation, and what happens to diasporic identity when the native tongue is silenced on the page?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Postcolonial Language Politics and the Norm of Code-Switching

From the inception of Postcolonial literary studies linguistic choices have served as a core area in decolonial scholarship marking the quest for native voice and cultural struggle. Ngũgĩ wa Thiong'o's (1986) insistence on abandoning English for African varieties has reaffirmed this claim. Writing in the colonizer's voice risk severing a people from their memory and local idiosyncracies. Along the similar lines, Ashcroft et al. (1989) theorized abrogation and appropriation, arguing that writers could seize English and bend it toward local purposes, an argument that made textual experimentation legible as resistance. Homi Bhabha's (1994) idea of third space deepened this logic by locating political power in hybridity itself. Within this framework, code-switching, lexical borrowing, and untranslated lexicon and syntax became recognizable as choices to extend agency (Kachru, 1986; Anzaldúa, 1987; Pratt, 1991). Sociolinguistic and stylistic accounts (Bandia, 2008; Myers-Scotton, 1993; Bhatt & Bolonyai, 2011) codified these moves as positive signals where the writer politicizes the practice of writing precisely where the text shifts between different languages or varieties of it.

Yet the success of this framework has resulted into a paradox. As multilingual expression became a common feature in postcolonial literature, it gradually turned into a fixed convention—a quick, recognizable way for readers and publishers to identify a work as authentic. Mufti (2016) calls for attention towards how the exotic can be curated for global consumption; Venuti (1995) describes the foreignizing effect that sells difference while still centering the Anglophone reader's comfort. In other words, code-switching can risk turning into a market friendly symbol instead of a form of resistance. This article challenges that comfort with multilingualism by pointing what happens when a postcolonial writer purposely avoids using multiple languages or varieties and how that refusal pushes us to rethink what we take for granted about the politics of language.

Linguistic Plurality to Global Legibility

Running alongside postcolonial celebrations of hybridity is a world-literature discourse that tracks the ascendancy of a globally legible, frictionless prose. Walkowitz's (2015) concept of the born-translated novel identifies texts engineered from the start for transnational circulation—often smoothing or pre-translating local idiom to maximize reach. Damrosch (2003) and Casanova (2004) map how works accumulate symbolic capital in a world republic of letters precisely by being readable across contexts, while Moretti (2013) explores the portability of forms that travel well. Rosa (2019) sharpens this insight with the idea of formal leveling: stylistic differences are flattened so that prose can slide more easily through global markets. Apter (2013) critiques this process for commodifying difference and erasing the politics of untranslatability; Mufti (2016) similarly warns that the world-lit machine can digest cultural specificity into palatable sameness. Yildiz's (2012) formulation of the postmonolingual condition provides a crucial conceptual hinge. Even as we celebrate multilingual realities, the ideology of one language—one nation remains embedded in institutions readership expectations. Monolingual norms are destabilized conceptually but persist materially. Apter (2013) emphasizes this with her focus on untranslatability. She concludes that some things resist being carried over without residue, and the pressure to smooth them out is political. Venuti's (1995) critique of fluency makes the same point from translation studies, the more invisible the mediation, the more dominant norms are naturalized.

Silence, Erasure, and Strategic Withholding

Silence is never empty of meaning. Feminist and postcolonial theorists such as Minh-ha (1989) and Spivak (1988) argue that the refusal to speak in expected ways can be a stylistic technique with an underlying purpose. Trauma theory (Caruth, 1996; LaCapra, 2001) note how ellipses and understatement signal an affective excess that language cannot bear. In this context, Hamid's (2017) silence around the mother tongue becomes legible as strategic withholding: rather than display linguistic difference for recognition points, the novel obliges readers to confront the flatness imposed by border regimes and by the literary marketplace. At the same time, Critical Discourse Analysis (Fairclough, 1995; Wodak & Meyer, 2009; van Dijk, 1993) warns that erasure and smoothing can reproduce dominance by making certain differences invisible. This is the double edge of language flattening: it resists exoticization but risks reinscribing hegemonic visibility regimes. Riaz et al. (2025) show how formal economy recalibrates affect and power, confirming that pared-down style is not neutral but politically saturated. In *Exit West*, smoothness is the message: it points to what has been ironed out, and asks why.

Diaspora, Identity, and the Affective Work of Language

Diaspora scholarship consistently links language, memory, and identity. Hall (1990) conceives identity as a positioning—constructed through history, culture, and discourse—while Brah (1996) and Gilroy (1993) illuminate how diasporic subjects inhabit “diaspora space” or a Black Atlantic where routes matter as much as roots. Pavlenko (2004, 2006) documents how bilinguals narrate selfhood through choice of tongue, and Butler (2004) reminds us that grievability—whose loss is recognized—depends on discursive frames. Boym's (2001) notion of “reflective nostalgia” helps parse the novel's affective temperature: longing is mediated, distanced, pondered rather than theatrically performed. Muñoz (1999) adds that affect can be futurity oriented; melancholic registers point to desires not yet realized. In *Exit West*, idiomatic traces are muted, producing a melancholic undertow: identity is displaced geographically and linguistically. The absent mother tongue functions as an affective index—its silence registers detachment, compromise, and survival rather than flamboyant assertion. Simon's (1999) “Other tongue” is present only as specter—a haunt that shapes but does not speak. Language flattening here is not just market savvy; it is a way of narrating what it means to live when one's sonic home has been stripped away.

Stylistics, Form, and the Micro-Politics of Diction

Recent “formalist turns” in postcolonial and global fiction studies insist that politics reside at the micro-level of syntax, lexis, and narration (Goyal, 2018; Boone, 2014). Leech and Short's (2007) stylistics provides the toolkit: sentence length, parataxis, generalization, deictic choices—all generate reader effects with ideological weight. Minimalism scholarship (Hallett, 1999; DelConte, 2008) confirms that so-called “plain style” is never plain; it can signal ethical restraint, respect for trauma's ineffability, or, conversely, moral evasion and affective chill. *Exit West*'s long, flowing, often hypotactic sentences universalize experience and smooth over particularities where we might expect dense idiom. Juxtaposing this with Rushdie's *Midnight's Children* (1981) or Adichie's *Americanah* (2013) throws Hamid's divergence into relief. Computational/stylistic work (Shen, Zhao, & Zaib, 2025) further shows that simplicity is a “thick aesthetic signal,” modulating empathy and authority. In Hamid, “minimalist idiom” and “tonal detachment” are calibrated—not default settings but deliberate techniques that carry political and affective freight.

METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative, single-text case study approach to analyze Mohsin Hamid's (2017) *Exit West* through the lens of postcolonial language politics and postmonolingual theory. The focus is on Hamid's use of language flattening, a deliberate stylistic strategy that avoids code-switching, idiomatic texture, and vernacular specificity in favor of a smooth, globally legible prose style. The analysis is grounded in close reading techniques, attending to formal and stylistic choices such as narrative voice, diction, syntactic simplicity, and the conscious absence of multilingual markers. These elements are not treated as neutral or incidental, but rather as aesthetic and political choices that reflect broader meanings in transnational literature.

The methodology draws on conceptual tools from postcolonial literary theory (e.g., Spivak, Bhabha), translation and world literature studies (e.g., Apter's born translated aesthetic, Walkowitz's translatability), and language ideology scholarship (e.g., Yildiz's postmonolingual condition). These frameworks allow the analysis to move beyond content to interrogate how form participates in shaping the novel's ethical and political stance. While limited to a single text, this case study is intended to serve as a model for analyzing similar stylistic phenomena in other transnational Anglophone novels. The study also opens space for future comparative research and reader-response investigations into how such language flattening is received by global audience.

Analysis

This analysis traces language flattening in four interconnected themes: the clear absence of the protagonists' native languages, the use of plain English that most readers can follow, a detached narrator that lowers emotion and keeps readers at a distance, and the resulting reshaping of diasporic identity. Together these elements reinforce one another, so the literature makes silence about language not incidental but central to meaning.

Absence of the Native Language

Exit West withholds Arabic, Urdu, Persian, or any other likely variety of its unnamed city. There are no glossaries, italicized insertions, or local words pointing towards the absence being systematic. When Nadia first appears "wearing a black robe, not for reasons of faith, but for a reason of her own" (Hamid, 2017, p. 17), the sentence indexes cultural practice but refrains from the usage of local lexicon or giving linguistic depth through a locally developed syntax. Along the similar lines, the narrator remains firm in his usage of English, creating a sense of dissonance from the protagonist. In another instance, Saeed's father spoke to his son at length before the lovers flee (Hamid, 2017, p. 83), yet the speech is reported in paraphrased form, with no orthographic trace of a mother tongue. In parallel, bureaucratic and mundane encounters such as ordering food, seeking shelter, negotiating work unfold without the any translated version with no instance of miscomprehension. The novel thus erases moments where code-switching would have plausibly emerged in lived migrant experience.

Ngũgĩ wa Thiong'o's (1986) insistence that language is the carrier of culture emphasizes how erasing or substituting tongues can sever memory. Here, however, substitution is not imposed but rather is assimilated in a seamlessly smooth and natural form. Yildiz's (2012) postmonolingual condition helps make sense of this: monolingual norms persist even when multilingual realities are acknowledged. As Simon (1999) notes, untranslated words leave a trace of the Other language which in the case of *Exit West* is not present. This absence also aligns with Trinh T. Minh-ha's (1989) notion of speaking nearby, not speaking about. The notions centres around the claim that the narrative do talk about cultural specificity but is without a sense of ownership. Yet, unlike Minh-ha's feminist poetics, Hamid's choice reads less as refusal to pin down and more as enforced neutrality. It stages a world in which the mother tongue has been flattened into an unmarked English in order to move across the borders and within global markets. (Mufti, 2016; Venuti, 1995).

Minimalist, Global English

The novel's diction and syntax extend this flattening. Sentences typically flow in long, additive clauses, but the vocabulary remains plain, abstract, and universally legible. Proper nouns are sparse with rare descriptive density. Places become "a camp," "a house," "a room," or "a city," often without culturally marked lexical items. Saeed and Nadia travel from an unnamed city to Mykonos, London, Marin, each rendered as mere points as part of a larger journey than as culturally rich local references. The effect mirrors Marc Augé's notion of non-places, spaces of transience that do not hold enough significance to be regarded as "places." Linguistically, these become irrelevant and generic signifiers that carry little cultural significance.

Minimalism in global English has been discussed as both access and assimilation (Walkowitz, 2015; Rosa, 2019). In *Exit West*, the simplicity is double-edged. On one hand, it allows readers from various contexts to feel and enjoy the text without lexical barriers. On the other, it universalizes experience, neutralizing the idiosyncracies that would have deepened the narrative. Consider the sentence: "The world was once small and now it is large, and people move through it in search of safety" (paraphrased from Hamid, 2017). The language is brief and emotionally flat creating an ease of translation. It presents refugee movement as a universal experience, not one tied to any specific culture or place. Another study by Shen et al. (2025)'s study of cultural aesthetics in language use across narrative media emphasizes that even stylistically plain text can encode aesthetic choices. The minimization of culturally specific lexemes also affects pronoun reference and deixis. "They," "we," and "people" proliferate, flattening distinctions among migrants, locals, hosts. While this produces solidarity at the level of discourse, it also risks what Butler (2004) might call a differential grievability problem i.e when everyone is "people," whose loss is legible and of value.

Narrative Detachment and Emotional Distance

The narrative voice in *Exit West* maintains a deliberate and consistent distance, rarely shifting into the intimate registers that might expose the protagonists' internal linguistic landscapes. Instances of free indirect discourse, when they do appear, are rendered in the same neutral, globally legible English as the primary narration. There is no movement into character-specific idioms or vernacular thought. This stylistic restraint aligns with the minimalist aesthetics described by Hallett (1999), wherein emotional intensity emerges through sparseness and control. In the

case of *Exit West*, however, this minimalism is deeply intertwined with a politics of linguistic flattening; the two operate in tandem, reinforcing one another throughout the text.

Emotional detachment is not in its entirety with instances of grief, fear, tenderness present but the language of those emotions is generalized. Saeed “missed his father,” Nadia “felt afraid,” they “argued less frequently” (Hamid, 2017, pp. 120–150). The verbs are basic with few modifiers. In trauma studies, such instances can signal numbing (Caruth, 1996). It is also performing the same dislocation here with affect being present but the syntax that would make it culturally resonant is absent. The couple’s emotional drift parallels their linguistic drift; as they move farther from home, both their speech and feeling flatten. Riaz et al. (2025) note how formal economy recalibrates affect and power dynamics in contemporary fiction. Applied to *Exit West*, the economy of language modulates empathy. the prose’s evenness keeps them slightly at bay, producing what Bellin (2022) terms disorienting empathy.

Detachment becomes most evident in the novel’s depiction of communal and relational breakdown. In London, as the protagonists gradually grow apart, their conversations remain flat and reportorial. There is no eruption into idiomatic quarrels, nor do any private jokes endure. The absence of their shared linguistic repertoire reflects a deeper loss of emotional connection. In this sense, language is not merely missing from the page, it has also diminished between them. The narrative tone formally encodes this erosion, and because the novel withholds any vivid portrayal of their earlier intimacy, the dissolution that follows feels not only natural but predetermined.

Identity in Diaspora

In *Exit West*, identity emerges through movement and interpersonal roles rather than through explicit linguistic self-definition. Stuart Hall’s (1990) notion of identity as “positioning” is particularly relevant here: Saeed and Nadia transition through multiple roles—partners, migrants, employees, strangers—yet the reader is never given access to their linguistic self-positioning. We never see them sharing colloquialisms, reflecting on their native language, or translating for others. The kinds of linguistic exchanges that typically signal diasporic identity in fiction are notably absent. This absence carries an ambivalent weight. On one hand, it mirrors the lived experience of displacement, where survival may necessitate the use of lingua francas and the suppression of personal idiom. On the other hand, it abstracts and generalizes diaspora, shifting it from specific, embodied experience to universalized archetype. Whereas Boym’s (2001) concept of reflective nostalgia emphasizes vivid, language-rich memory, Hamid’s characters remember in flat, undifferentiated English. The resonant sounds of home—street cries, familial expressions, religious language—are missing. As a result, nostalgia becomes spatial rather than linguistic; “the city” replaces culturally specific evocations of home. In this framework, identity becomes a matter of drift rather than of dialogic engagement.

The narrative’s conclusion, marked by the calm and courteous separation of Nadia and Saeed, reinforces this reading. Their parting is understated, with little remaining linguistic imprint of their shared past. Muñoz’s (1999) theory of “disidentifications”—modes of resisting assimilation through subversive engagement with dominant discourse—might suggest a possibility for such resistance through language. Yet Hamid offers no such linguistic resistance; instead, identity work is externalized through their actions—volunteering, working—rather than through speech. The absence of the mother tongue, then, is more than symbolic erasure; it reflects a broader redefinition of identity practice in conditions of global instability.

A critical discourse analysis perspective further clarifies this dynamic. Ahmed et al. (2025) demonstrate how the discourse of colonialism often normalizes dispossession through neutral tones and silences, showing that power frequently operates through what appears to be common sense and through what is left unspoken. This framework invites a reading of Hamid’s minimalist prose not merely as stylistic preference but as political strategy (Hallett, 1999). Riaz et al. (2025) show how compressed form can shape emotional and political landscapes. In *Exit West*, the short, loosely connected sentences and generalized vocabulary generate a fluid reading experience that both enables global readability and quietly questions its implications. Ultimately, the novel laments the cost of becoming universally legible. As Ahmed et al. (2025) caution, the same even tone that smooths prose can also smooth over dispossession—revealing the deep entanglement of literary form and political discourse.

CONCLUSION

Mohsin Hamid’s *Exit West* refrains from multilingual attributes of a postcolonial novel by offering a plain and globally accessible form of English language. The analysis situates *Exit West* at the crossroads of postcolonial language politics, global literary scholarship, and diasporic identity formation. This article theorizes language

flattening as a deliberate stylistic subtraction in *Exit West*, challenging a critical consensus that equates visible multilingualism with resistance. By mapping four dimensions—absence, minimalism, detachment, and identity softening—the study demonstrates how omission can function as both critique and complicity within global literary markets. Future research can test the argument across a comparative corpus and incorporate studies to gauge how readers process this flattened style. Ultimately, language flattening offers critics a portable tool to reassess not only what is said in postcolonial texts, but what is strategically left unsaid.

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